

ALGORITHMIC FOLKLØRE

Lexicon 1.0

Gabriele de Seta

Marianne Gunderson

Debarun Sarkar

Yağmur Çisem Vik

Hanna Hellesø Lauvli

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CREDITS

Gabriele de Seta
Marianne Gunderson
Hanna Hellesø Lauvli
Debarun Sarkar
Yağmur Çisem Vik

Illustrations: Hanna Hellesø Lauvli
Font: Uncanny Hiccups by Drew Sisk

ABOUT

This lexicon is one of the outcomes of the research project “Algorithmic Folklore: The mutual shaping of vernacular creativity and automation” (ALGOFOLK), a four-year TMF-funded project led by Gabriele de Seta, researching the complex relationships between creative practices and algorithmic systems. The lexicon stands as a resource for key terms within the field of Digital Culture with specific focus on terminology related to the concept of algorithmic folklore.

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ALGORITHMIC FOLKLORE: The mutual shaping of vernacular creativity and automation

Are machines creative? Can algorithms make art? Will AI replace human invention?

These are the wrong questions. The ALGOFOLK project argues that a more productive way to approach these issues is by unpacking both sides of the *automation = creativity* equation, and accounting for what is already happening at their articulation through the highly specialized toolbox offered by human and social science approaches to technology.

As algorithmic systems become widely adopted across the globe, profoundly impacting both cultural industries and everyday media practices, it is urgent to understand the emerging relationship between *creativity* and *automation*. This interdisciplinary project seeks to theorize this relationship through the concept of algorithmic folklore.

Algorithmic folklore operationalizes the idea that automated systems like recommendation engines and machine learning models give rise to new kinds of *vernacular creativity* – ordinary creative practices emerging outside the scope of professional and cultural recognition. The relationship between algorithmic automation and vernacular creativity has yet to be properly conceptualized.

ALGOFOLK will fill this gap by proposing that algorithmic folklore articulates creativity and automation through a process of *mutual shaping*. The project's overarching research question is: How do algorithms shape people's everyday creativity, and how do creative practices shape automated systems? This question will be answered through a global and comparative study.

Examples of algorithmic folklore that this project will collect, analyze and compare include: the urban legends through which users make sense of machine learning models such as GPT-4; the folk theories through which people interpret the decisions of social media algorithms such as TikTok's video recommendation; or the cycles of humorous memes co-created through generative artificial intelligence tools.

This project will impact both academic and public debates about the role of technological automation in society in three ways:

1. The theorization of algorithmic folklore will advance current understandings of how people creatively respond to automated systems;
2. The global comparative scope of the project will expand scholarly knowledge of creative production beyond anglocentric contexts;
3. The archival collection of algorithmic folklore will document an important moment in the history of digital culture.

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ALGORITHMIC CULTURE

Algorithmic culture indicates both the historical moment in which cultural products and practices are increasingly shaped by algorithms, as well as the cultural phenomena emerging around algorithmic systems.

Since the beginning of the 21st century, the widespread adoption of computational technologies has brought more and more people in direct contact with algorithms and their effects on culture. Through his analysis of videogames as cultural objects, media theorist Alexander R. Galloway has introduced the concept of “algorithmic culture” to describe the historical moment characterized by “a dazzling new array of cultural phenomena, from the cut-up sampling culture of hip-hop to the calculus curves of computer-aided architectural design” (2006, 17) made possible by digital information processing.

With the popularization of algorithmic processes including predictive analytics, approximation techniques, social graphs and recommender systems, Galloway’s intuition was echoed across fields. In software studies, theorist Andrew Goffey argues that analyzing the social and material effects of algorithms on their users can help understand “major elements of the concept of culture as a response to the abstract machinery of industrial capitalism” (Goffey 2008, 19). Similarly, cultural studies scholars have also connected the rules-based decision-making processes that characterize algorithmic systems to new algorithmic identities that challenge established categories such as individuality and participation (Cheney-Lippold 2011, 178).

In the mid-2010s, mounting evidence indicated that algorithms had become an issue of public interest: as the internet transformed from an infrastructure for connection to one structured by sorting, with most of the content experienced by users being mediated by algorithmic systems for content recommendation and collaborative filtering on platforms such as Amazon, Google or Netflix, “the algorithm” emerged as a contested cultural object, particularly as commercial entities appropriated the concept from computer science for promotional purposes (Sandvig 2014). Tarleton Gillespie calls this “the relevance of algorithms”: the fact that “as we have embraced computational tools as our primary media of expression [...] we are subjecting human discourse and

knowledge to these procedural logics that undergird all computation” (Gillespie 2014, 168).

As specific discursive formations consolidate around algorithms, their role in society is unavoidably connected to the relationship between knowledge and power – in David Beer’s words:

The notion of the ‘algorithm’ is now taking on its own force, as a kind of evocative shorthand for the power and potential of calculative systems that can think more quickly, more comprehensively and more accurately than humans. [...] The algorithm is now a cultural presence, perhaps even an iconic cultural presence, not just because of what they can do but also because of what the notion of the algorithm is used to project. (2017, 11).

Nick Seaver describes this condition by differentiating between two approaches that he terms “algorithms in culture” and “algorithms as culture” (Seaver 2017). The former does not see algorithms as part of culture, but rather as stable technical objects that can operate within cultural contexts, while the latter emphasizes their instability and situatedness as part of cultural practices – as he concludes, “algorithms are cultural not because they work on things like movies or music, or because they become objects of popular concern, but because they are composed of collective human practices. Algorithms are multiple, like culture, because they *are* culture” (Seaver 2017, 5). This perspective has important implications for the study of algorithms in everyday life situations, including the cultural imaginaries that develop around them as people encounter them and try to make sense of their operations (Bucher 2016).

REFERENCES

Beer, David. 2017. “The Social Power of Algorithms.” *Information, Communication & Society* 20 (1): 1–13.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1216147>

Bucher, Taina. 2016. “Neither Black nor Box: Ways of Knowing Algorithms.” In *Innovative Methods in Media and Communication Research*, edited by Sebastian Kubitschko and Anne Kaun. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-40700-5_5

Cheney-Lippold, John. 2011. “A New Algorithmic Identity: Soft Biopolitics and the Modulation of Control.” *Theory, Culture & Society* 28 (6): 164–81.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0263276411424420>

Galloway, Alexander R. 2006. *Gaming: Essays on Algorithmic Culture*. Electronic Mediations 18. University of Minnesota Press.

Gillespie, Tarleton. 2014. "The Relevance of Algorithms." In *Media Technologies: Essays on Communication, Materiality, and Society*, edited by Tarleton Gillespie, Pablo J. Boczkowski, and Kirsten A. Foot. Inside Technology, edited by Wiebe E. Bijker, W. Bernard Carlson, and Trevor Pinch. MIT Press.

Goffey, Andrew. 2008. "Algorithm." In *Software Studies: A Lexicon*, edited by Matthew Fuller. Leonardo, edited by Roger F. Malina and Sean Cubitt. MIT Press.

Sandvig, Christian. 2014. "Seeing the Sort: The Aesthetic and Industrial Defense of 'the Algorithm.'" *Media-N: Journal of the New Media Caucus* 10 (3).

<https://median.newmediacaucus.org/art-infrastructures-information/seeing-the-sort-the-aesthetic-and-industrial-defense-of-the-algorithm/>

Seaver, Nick. 2017. "Algorithms as Culture: Some Tactics for the Ethnography of Algorithmic Systems." *Big Data & Society* 4 (2): 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951717738104>

ALGORITHMIC FOLKLORE

The concept of algorithmic folklore can be interpreted in two ways: folklore that develops around algorithms, or folklore that has algorithmic features. In both senses, it captures the emergence of informal vernacular creative practices inflected by the growing global relevance of algorithmic media.

The relationship between folklore and algorithms can be traced back to the development of an algorithmic culture that directly connects medieval mathematics to contemporary computational technologies (Striphas 2023). Early examples of folklore about calculation include stories such as “The Chessboard of Sissah”, which describes how the inventor of the game of chess tricked an Indian king with the principle of exponential duplication, making him promise to double one grain of wheat for each square of the board (Bardi 2025). Folklore about algorithmic processes also includes myths, legends, traditions and rituals: as Matteo Pasquinelli demonstrates through his analysis of the Vedic ritual Agnicayana, rules-based problem-solving thinking and practices “have been part of all cultures and civilizations” (Pasquinelli 2023, 28).

With the advent of calculating machines and computational technologies, folklore about algorithms has expanded to the domains of computer software, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. In a 2021 essay, researchers Ireti Akinrinade and Joan Mukogosi coin the term “algorithmic folklore” to illustrate how teenagers interacting with TikTok’s recommender system and trying to reverse-engineer it also engage in the production of strategic knowledge: “[b]y sharing experiences, asking questions, and crowdsourcing answers, teens are developing an algorithmic folklore while discerning the potential motivations behind TikTok’s software engineering” (2021).

Researchers working across disciplines have also arrived at this concept to define similar phenomena. Laura Savolainen, for example, examines the informal “beliefs and stories about algorithmic governance” through which Reddit users discuss the dynamics of platform moderation (Savolainen 2022, 1096). Minna Ruckenstein’s 2023 book *The Feel of Algorithms*, based on extensive interviews with Finnish people about their encounters with algorithms, foregrounds algorithmic folklore as a key form of literacy to be taken seriously (2023, 55). Folklore scholar Guro Flinterud theorizes how algorithms not only become part of

folklore, but also play a role in its production and dissemination (2023, 454). Gabriele de Seta makes a similar point by defining algorithmic folklore as the repertoire of genres and practices that emerge from encounters between vernacular creativity and computational automation: “algorithms are not just a topic of vernacular creativity, but become its technological medium and actively participate in the creation and circulation of content” (2024, 240).

As technological innovations like distributed computation, sensing infrastructures, deep learning and automated agents become pervasive and their operations acquire relevance for societies around the globe, algorithmic folklore is not limited to explanations of search engine behavior or beliefs about social media recommendation, but rather scales up into a domain of creative literacy production applicable to a world mediated by calculative regimes. In short, the more human experience is mediated by systems based on rule-based problem-solving, the more algorithmic folklore becomes a useful category to understand and conceptualize the new kinds of narratives, beliefs and practices developing around and through these systems.

REFERENCES

- Akinrinade, Iretholu, and Joan Mukogosi. 2021. “Strategic Knowledge.” *Data & Society: Points*, July 16.
<https://medium.com/datasociety-points/strategic-knowledge-6bbddb3f0259>.
- Bardi, Alberto. 2025. “Mathematics and Cultures across the Chessboard: The Wheat and Chessboard Problem Revisited.” In *Handbook of the Mathematics of the Arts and Sciences*, edited by Bharath Sriraman. Springer Nature Switzerland.
- de Seta, Gabriele. 2024. “An Algorithmic Folklore: Vernacular Creativity in Times of Everyday Automation.” In *Critical Meme Reader III: Breaking the Meme*, edited by Chloë Arkenbout and Idil Galip. Institute of Network Cultures.
- Flinterud, Guro. 2023. “‘Folk’ in the Age of Algorithms: Theorizing Folklore on Social Media Platforms.” *Folklore* 134 (4): 439–61.
- Pasquinelli, Matteo. 2023. *The Eye of the Master: A Social History of Artificial Intelligence*. Verso.
- Ruckenstein, Minna. 2023. *The Feel of Algorithms*. University of California Press.

Algorithmic Folklore Lexicon 1.0

Savolainen, Laura. 2022. "The Shadow Banning Controversy: Perceived Governance and Algorithmic Folklore." *Media, Culture & Society* 44 (6): 1091–109.

Striphas, Ted. 2023. *Algorithmic Culture before the Internet*. Columbia University Press

ALGOSPEAK

Algospeak is the multimodal lexicon developed by users to ensure successful communication with their intended audiences while also avoiding, countering or manipulating automated processes such as content analysis, moderation, recommendation and filtering.

Computational technologies and networked communications have consistently shaped language. From the netspeak and chatspeak of the early internet to the lolspeak and leetspeak of social media and online videogames, users develop new linguistic forms to signal their belonging to a speech community. This "language of the internet" (Crystal 2001) often develops as a way to establish social boundaries or signal generational identities, but it can also function to avoid surveillance, censorship or prosecution in contexts where speech is policed.

The growing presence of automated decision-making systems in everyday life - from text processing and social media recommendation to content moderation and language modeling - gives rise to new kinds of linguistic innovations (Gerrard 2018). For example, the popularization of personalized social media feeds has been linked to the emergence of a lexicon developed by users in order to evade, counter or manipulate the algorithmic recommendation or moderation of the content they produce (Calhoun & Fawcett 2023).

The term 'algospeak' was coined in the early 2020s to describe responses to the centrality of content analysis, recommendation and filtering systems on TikTok; popular media discussions describe it as "code words or turns of phrase users have adopted in an effort to create a brand-safe lexicon that will avoid getting their posts removed or down-ranked by content moderation systems" (Lorenz 2022). These systems, which are often opaque and unpredictable, often further marginalize groups discussing sensitive topics such as sex work, mental health or self-harm (Schock et al. 2024).

The key difference between algospeak and previous kinds of internet languages is that algospeak is not only directed to human addressees, but also to algorithmic systems. In terms of formal features, algospeak adopts multiple strategies like substituting letters with numeric characters, punctuation or other symbols; censoring through bleeping, strikethrough or blurring; replacing words with others or with emoji. Classic examples of algospeak include 'unalive' for suicide or homicide, 'corn' for porn', and 'leg booty' for L.G.B.T.Q. (Kreuz 2023).

Academic research on algospeak mainly conceptualizes it in relation to TikTok's moderation system, as "the practices of intentionally shortening, misspelling, or substituting specific words as part of creating and sharing content" (Klug et al. 2023, 234) that users develop in order to avoid the platform's algorithmic filtering, which they perceive as "non-contextual, random, inaccurate, or biased, and therefore unjust" (Steen et al. 2023, 12). Algospeak is therefore a temporary countermeasure that evolves alongside TikTok's moderation practices, and which goes beyond the simple replacement of letters or words, to also include emoji, gestures, and modes of speech like whispering. As Steen and coauthors argue,

the existing definition of algospeak needs to be enhanced, and algospeak needs to be understood as code words and linguistic variations, visual and multimodal communication, and audiovisual coherences in social media interaction (Steen et al. 2023, 12)

Algospeak use has been documented across linguistic and political divides: alt-right communities bypass platform regulations by encoding white supremacist slogans into numbers (Hagman 2024); dozens of algospeak variations of 'Israel' and 'Palestine' are used to bypass content filtering during heated social media discussions about the conflict (Isam 2024); Turkish users develop 'algorithm repellent' terms to evade local content restrictions (de Seta et al. 2026).

The controversial status of algospeak gives rise to a cat and mouse game between users and platforms - in Adam Aleksic's words, "[w]ords aren't just diffusing from human to human anymore. They're now moving from human to algorithm and back to human (2025, 113). Confronted with this challenge to moderation systems and its potential for abusive, harmful or criminal uses, computer scientists propose to utilize large language models (LLMs) for the detection and unmasking of algospeak (Fillies & Paschke 2024). At the same time, critical AI scholars note that the emergence of these linguistic innovations evidences the stark difference between humans and machines, as "LLMs can't algospeak" (Birhane & McGann 2024).

REFERENCES

Aleksic, Adam. 2025. *Algospeak: How Social Media Is Transforming the Future of Language*. Alfred A. Knopf.

Birhane, Abeba, and Marek McGann. 2024. "Large Models of What? Mistaking Engineering Achievements for Human Linguistic

Agency.” *Language Sciences* 106 (November): 1–13.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.langsci.2024.101672>

Calhoun, Kendra, and Alexia Fawcett. 2023. “They Edited out Her Nip Nops’: Linguistic Innovation as Textual Censorship Avoidance on TikTok.” *Language@Internet* 21: 1–30.

<https://doi.org/10.14434/li.v21.37371>

Fillies, Jan, and Adrian Paschke. 2024. “Simple LLM Based Approach to Counter Algospeak.” *Proceedings of the 8th Workshop on Online Abuse and Harms (WOAH 2024)*, 136–45.

<https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/2024.woah-1.10>

Gerrard, Ysabel. 2018. “Beyond the Hashtag: Circumventing Content Moderation on Social Media.” *New Media & Society* 20 (12): 4492–511. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444818776611>

Hagman, Malvin. 2024. “Algorithmic Tolerance of Human Intolerance: An Explorative Study on the Proliferation of the Alt-Right’s Abuse of TikTok’s Algorithmic Content Moderation System.” Master Thesis, Örebro University.

Isam, Hishamudin. 2024. “Algospeak and Digital Culture: Navigating Social Media Challenges.” In *Proceedings of the Third International Conference on Communication, Language, Literature, and Culture (ICCoLLiC 2024)*, edited by Zita Rarastesa, Radhika Gajjala, Hishamudin Isam, and Djatmika Djatmika. Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research 883. Atlantis Press SARL. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-321-4_50

Klug, Daniel, Ella Steen, and Kathryn Yurechko. 2023. “How Algorithm Awareness Impacts Algospeak Use on TikTok.” *Companion Proceedings of the ACM Web Conference 2023*, 234–37. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3543873.3587355>

Kreuz, Roger J. 2023. “What Is ‘Algospeak’? Inside the Newest Version of Linguistic Subterfuge.” *The Conversation*, April 13. <http://theconversation.com/what-is-algospeak-inside-the-newest-version-of-linguistic-subterfuge-203460>

Lorenz, Taylor. 2022. “Internet ‘Algospeak’ Is Changing Our Language in Real Time, from ‘Nip Nops’ to ‘Le Dollar Bean.’” *The Washington Post*, April 8. <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2022/04/08/algospeak-tiktok-le-dollar-bean/>

Steen, Ella, Kathryn Yurechko, and Daniel Klug. 2023. “You Can (Not) Say What You Want: Using Algospeak to Contest and Evade Algorithmic Content Moderation on TikTok.” *Social Media + Society* 9 (3): 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231194586>

CREATIVITY

Creativity is a slippery and multifaceted concept that is defined across disciplines as either a property, process,, social relation, or cultural construct, and is shaped by both its historical invention and by economic discourses that link it to value production.

Creativity is notoriously difficult to define, and substantive scholarship across fields is devoted to provide structural scaffolding for this concept by either establishing its relationship to similar concepts (originality, innovation, unpredictability), or by unpacking it in more nuanced categories. A key handbook in the field of creativity studies exemplifies the first approach: “Creativity consists of at least four components: (1) the creative process, (2) the creative product, (3) the creative person, and (4) the creative situation” (Brown 1989, 3), while anthropologist Eitan Wilf exemplifies the latter in defining creativity as:

communicative, interactional, and improvisational events, with real-time emergent properties, involving human and nonhuman agents in the context of pre-existing yet malleable genres, conventions, and constraints. (Wilf 2014, 398)

In psychology, the standard definition of creativity privileges novelty and usefulness as the two key components (Runco & Jaeger 2012). Creativity must lead to the development of a material or mental outcome which is original and deemed useful by domain experts. Anthropology privileges a more relational view that acknowledges the coexistence of multiple forms of creativity as well as the situated and contextual nature of this concept (Moeran 2016). In sociology, creativity is approached as a historically constructed concept intimately connected to Western modernity (Reckwitz 2017).

In the post-industrial era, creativity has become intimately connected to influential buzzwords such as creative class, creative cities and creative clusters (Florida 2012), emerging as an imagined source of value generation leading to shifts in both education and the workplace. Critical evaluations of this phenomenon have led to outright opposition or even dismissal of creativity as a moral injunction in favor of a more ethical notion of inventiveness (Osborne 2003).

REFERENCES

- Brown, Robert. T. 1989. *Creativity: What Are We To Measure?* In J. A. Glover, R. R. Ronning, & C. R. Reynolds (Eds.), *Handbook of Creativity* (pp. 3–32). Springer US. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4757-5356-1_1
- Florida, Richard. 2012. *The Rise of the Creative Class, Revisited*. 10th anniversary ed. Basic Books.
- Moeran, Brian. 2016. *The Business of Creativity: Toward an Anthropology of Worth*. Routledge.
- Osborne, Thomas. 2003. Against ‘creativity’: A philistine rant. *Economy and Society*, 32(4), 507–525. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0308514032000141684>
- Reckwitz, Andreas. 2017. *The Invention of Creativity: Modern Society and the Culture of the New*. Translated by Steven Black. Polity Press.
- Runco, Mark. A., & Jaeger, Garrett. J. 2012. The Standard Definition of Creativity. *Creativity Research Journal*, 24(1), 92–96. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10400419.2012.650092>
- Wilf, Eitan. 2014. Semiotic Dimensions of Creativity. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 43(1), 397–412. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-102313-030020>

DEAD INTERNET THEORY

The Dead Internet Theory postulates that an onslaught of bot activity and computer-generated content will eventually replace human interaction online with entirely artificial engagement.

Discourses surrounding the future of the Web have been present since before the Web's inception. Early adopters foresaw a future where the Web would close the divide of class, gender and race, whereas sceptics feared a neo-liberal agenda taking hold (Lovink 2009, 5). In 2010—on the 20th anniversary of the Web—Tim Berners-Lee expressed concern about the looming dangers of surveillance of government institutions, Internet providers slowing traffic to select sites, and social media networks gatekeeping information (2010, 80). While these fears remain, new conceptions and theories of online futures and ways of being have surfaced with the rise of automated content generation. After the launch of large language models, for example, Matthew Kirschenbaum wrote the now well-known essay “Prepare for the Textpocalypse” (2023) in which he presents a world at risk of being overexposed to immense quantities of machine-generated text, potentially threatening online authenticity, truth and estrangement. Before that, however, was the Dead Internet Theory.

Like many conspiracy theories, it is difficult to identify a single point of origin for the Dead Internet Theory, though imaginations about an internet wasteland have been circulating online for a while (Mariani 2023). The Dead Internet Theory as a singular theory, however, was introduced to - and then circulated by - many internet users after publication of the post "Dead Internet Theory: Most of the Internet is Fake" on Agora Road Macintosh Cafe, an online messaging board (IlluminatiPirate 2021). The original theory described an internet largely dominated by bots and automated activity, but still ultimately controlled by humans in powerful positions. While the post also contained several controversial claims – including dehumanizing language and moral-panic rhetoric to misrepresent transgender identities - the theory's widespread appeal centers primarily on this specific notion. Over time, discussions and communities surrounding the theory expanded its scope to include all forms of computer-generated content, particularly AI-generated material (e.g. the subreddit r/deadinternettheory).

Since posting in 2021, the post and subsequent replies highlight several distinctive features of the theory, namely that the rise of AI generated content is intentionally promoted by government institutions, is responsible for extreme political tensions, and is controlled by social media websites and search engine operators. The main culprit of the Dead Internet is said to be a mixture of obviously AI-generated and seemingly human-produced content that is in reality also synthetic. This, in turn, is making the web seem far more populated than it actually is. Proponents of this specific theory suggest the time of death happened somewhere between 2016-2017. Since posting, the theory has spread to news media outlets (Tiffany 2021; Hern 2024) and into pop culture.

Although not specifically named Dead Internet Theory, imaginations of what AI generated content is doing to the Web is making its way through popular channels. For example, astrophysicist and public figure Neil Degrasse Tyson suggested that true and false news will become so interchangeable we will no longer be able to trust anything we see online, and it will once again return to a sphere where cat-videos reign supreme (Lemon 2024, 14:00). Elsewhere, news outlets question the social in social media, reporting public concern as social media platforms implement AI in an attempt to "engage and entertain" to keep their user base on their platforms (Murphy and Criddle 2024). Alongside technological developments, the Dead Internet Theory has shifted from single-origin conspiracy theory to a more general folk theory on how algorithms change and shape the internet. Joint in their fear for the loss of authenticity, rise of false information and manipulative content, and a decline in communal engagement online, the Dead Internet Theory highlights a shift in both the production and consumption of content online.

REFERENCES

Berners-Lee, Tim. 2010. "LONG LIVE THE WEB." *Scientific American* 303, no. 6: 80–85.
<http://www.jstor.org/stable/26002308>.

Hern, Alex. 2024. «TechScape: On the Internet, Where Does the Line between Person End and Bot Begin?» *The Guardian*, 30. april 2024, paragr. Technology.
<https://www.theguardian.com/technology/2024/apr/30/techscape-artificial-intelligence-bots-dead-internet-theory>

- IlluminatiPirate. 2021. forum.agoraroad.com
<https://forum.agoraroad.com/index.php?threads/dead-internet-theory-most-of-the-internet-is-fake.3011/>
- Kirschenbaum, Matthew. 2023. «Prepare for the Textpocalypse». Technology. The Atlantic, march 8.
<https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2023/03/ai-chatgpt-writing-language-models/673318/>
- Lemon, Don. 2024. "Neil deGrasse Tyson says AI will KILL the INTERNET! | The Don Lemon Show". YouTube. April 17, 2024. Talkshow, 14:00. <https://youtu.be/SAuDmBYwLq4?si=1e-XwOZG3kBYdW8E&t=840Neil>
- Lovink, Geert. 2009. Dynamics of Critical Internet Culture (1994-2001). Instituteofnetworkcultures.
- Mariani, Robert. 2023. «The Dead Internet to Come». *The New Atlantis*, nr. 73, 34–42.
- Murphy, Hannah, and Cristina Criddle. 2024. «Meta envisages social media filled with AI-generated users». *Financial Times*, 27. desember 2024, pagr. Meta Platforms.
<https://www.ft.com/content/91183cbb-50f9-464a-9d2e-96063825bfcf>
- Tiffany, Kaitlyn. 2021. «Maybe You Missed It, but the Internet ‘Died’ Five Years Ago». *The Atlantic* (blog). 31. august 2021.
<https://www.theatlantic.com/technology/archive/2021/08/dead-internet-theory-wrong-but-feels-true/619937>

DIGITAL FOLKLORE

Digital folklore is the folklore of the internet, emerging from everyday online practices of vernacular creativity and coalescing into repertoires of jokes, memes, and other genres of digital content.

Digital folklore could seem like a paradoxical concept, as the two terms 'folklore' and 'digital' are often imagined to occupy opposite positions on multiple axes: tradition versus innovation, artisanal versus technological, past versus future. And yet, throughout the history of computation, the closeness between the digital and the folkloric has been repeatedly recognized by scholars, artists, and users alike. For example, in her analysis of genres like ASCII art, animated greeting cards and emoticons, sociologist Brenda Danet identifies these creative practices as an emergent form of folk art with striking similarities to traditional crafts like quilting or embroidering (2001, 274). Folklorist Monica Foote connects this "cyber folk art" to the affordances offered by networked communications, arguing that it should not be reduced to mere repetitions of existing folklore genres distributed through a new medium, as "those who frequent chat rooms, and use instant messenger programs have developed their own folkspeech, online communities function according to their own set of customary behavior, and people represent themselves with scraps of art cobbled together into images that distinguish themselves from their fellow users" (2007, 27). More and more researchers have recognized that genres like jokes, tales and folk beliefs have been consistently circulating online since the early 1990s, becoming a "technologically mediated folklore" (Howard 2008, 193) or a folklore of the internet (Blank 2009). In 2009, artists Olia Lialina and Dragan Espenschied published *Digital Folklore*, an edited volume including analyses of GeoCities homepages, custom fonts and animated GIFs which offers the first comprehensive definition of its titular term:

If computer technology has any cultural significance, it is indeed solely owed to its users. Yet their own creative efforts, from shiny-stars live wallpapers to pictures of cute cats or rainbow gradients, are mostly derided as kitsch or general cultural waste. *Digital Folklore* argues that this apparent aesthetic clutter, created by users for users, is the most important, beautiful and widely misunderstood language of New Media (Lialina & Espenschied 2009, fourth cover).

Throughout the 2010s, digital folklore has become more and more widespread as an analytical category and an expanding field of research across disciplines including anthropology and

folklore studies, media and cultural studies, aesthetics and design, art history, and communication studies. For example, since 2018, Lynne S. McNeill's Digital Folklore Project at Utah State University tracks and archives “trending memes, hashtags, urban legends, or other pieces of digital culture”; in 2024, The Folklore Society's Annual Conference was titled “Digital Folklore”, testifying to the disciplinary relevance of this concept. While research on digital folklore has partly bridged its apparent contradictions, its definition remains fluid and shifting alongside technological and societal developments. On the one hand, digital folklore is the folklore of the digital, a continuation of long-standing practices and genres of content through relatively new media; on the other, digital folklore is a stark break with the past, a new form of vernacular creativity made possible by computational technologies. Digital folklore might not become a lasting analytical concept, but it testifies to the widely recognized necessity for a descriptor combining the creative aspects of folklore, with the centrality of digital mediation in contemporary communication technologies (de Seta 2020).

REFERENCES

- Blank, Trevor J., ed. 2009. *Folklore and the Internet: Vernacular Expression in a Digital World*. Utah State University Press.
- Danet, Brenda. 2001. *Cyberpl@y: Communicating Online*. Berg.
- de Seta, Gabriele. 2020. “Digital Folklore.” In *Second International Handbook of Internet Research*, edited by Jeremy Hunsinger, Lisbeth Klastrup, and Matthew M. Allen, 167–180. Springer.
- Foote, Monica. 2007. “Userpicks: Cyber Folk Art in the Early 21st Century.” *Folklore Forum* 37, no. 1: 27–38.
- Howard, Robert Glenn. 2008. “Electronic hybridity: The Persistent Processes of the Vernacular Web.” *Journal of American Folklore* 121, no. 480: 192–218.
- Lialina, Olia, and Dragan Espenschied, eds. 2009. *Digital folklore*. Merz & Solitude.

ENSHITTIFICATION

Enshittification is the process platforms undergo when company stakeholders allocate more value towards themselves instead of the users, ultimately leading to the platform being deemed unusable and consequently abandoned.

The term enshittification originated in a blogpost by Cory Doctorow (2022) as a response to the mass exodus of the social networking sites Twitter and Facebook in the early 2020s. It is described as a three-step process on how media platforms inevitably make themselves undesirable to both users and business clients:

First, they are good to their users; then they abuse their users to make things better for their business customers; finally, they abuse those business customers to claw back all the value for themselves (Doctorow 2023)

As the platforms leverage network effects – where a service increases in value as more people use it, in turn making the cost of leaving higher than the cost of remaining – the process of enshittification occurs when platforms change their services to capture more of the value the users generate for them while reducing what they offer to users. By removing features, selling user attention and personal data to the highest bidders, pitting advertisers against each other, and other tactics, the platform services literally become shit, or *enshittify*.

The enshittification process affects all kinds of platforms – “from mobile app stores to Steam, from Facebook to Twitter”, as Doctorow puts it (2023). For e-commerce sites like Amazon, enshittification gradually turns into the platform into a place where sellers are forced to offer their lowest pricing while being outbid by the platform itself, where top searches and items are replaced with Amazon’s own versions, all while monopolizing a whole creator industry within it (Doctorow 2022). For social media sites, the process unfolds as it goes from a place of human connection to a place where you buy things.

With the massive adoption, technical possibilities, and use of Large Language Models, Toomas Timpka (2024) describes how the process of enshittification also affects the academic sphere through papermills selling manuscripts to LLM-assisted peer reviewing. With the constant push for better, quicker and cheaper labor, Timpka argues that unless both academic writers and institutions give focus to quality over quantity, both papermills and online journals are destined to fail through a process of enshittification (2024, 665).

Similarly, James Ryan (2024) predicts the coming demise of traditional internet search and e-commerce. With statistics showing the growth of chatbots over search engines Ryan suggests engines like Google Search may be at the later stages of enshittification – with the sponsored links and ads drowning out actual search results – chatbots are still in the first phase, or to put it simply, “they are [still] being good to their users” (Ryan 2024). Ryan demonstrates how the process of enshittification might be a useful method in predicting how new platforms and services will develop, making it a tool not only for past events, but current and future ones too.

REFERENCES

Doctorow, Cory. 2022. “Pluralistic: How Monopoly Enshittified Amazon/28 Nov 2022” – *Pluralistic: Daily Links from Cory Doctorow*. 2022. august 17.

<https://pluralistic.net/2022/11/28/enshittification/>.

Doctorow, Cory. 2022. «Social Quitting». Medium, november 17.

<https://doctorow.medium.com/social-quitting-1ce85b67b456>

Doctorow, Cory. 2023. «The ‘Enshittification’ of TikTok». Wired.

<https://www.wired.com/story/tiktok-platforms-cory-doctorow/>

Ryan, James. 2024. «The Coming Enshittification of AI: Will AI Follow Internet Search and e-Commerce down the Path of Enshittification, or Can We Finally Have Nice Things?» *The Journal of Business and Artificial Intelligence* 1 (2): 2.

<https://jbai.ai/index.php/jbai/article/view/31>

Timpka, Toomas. 2024. «The “Enshittification” of Online Information Services Obligates Rigorous Management of Scientific Journals». *Journal of Science and Medicine in Sport* 27 (10): 665–66. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsams.2024.08.208>.

FOLKLORE

Folklore refers to community practices that are deemed to be traditional, informal, non-official, non-scientific and ordinary. This includes a wide repertoire of shared genres such as jokes, proverbs, stories, legends, songs, and poems as well as material culture such as clothes, music, paintings, rituals, technology, dances and customary habits.

The term folklore was coined by British writer William John Thoms in 1846 to replace the less intuitive ‘popular antiquities’, which included the “manners, customs, observances, superstitions, ballads, proverbs, &c., of the olden time” (Merton 1846); after several attempts to popularize this term (Roper 2007), the neologism eventually resonated with readers and originated the discipline of folkloristics, which has retroactively applied it to traditions much older than the term itself (Emrich 1946).

The field of folklore studies flourished as a response to these supposed remnants of the past with an archival impulse of collecting. Like anthropology, folkloristics displayed a tendency of studying an ‘other’ even if the ‘other’ was often located within Europe. Peasants, the illiterate and minor ethnic groups, were a key obsession. Akin to the object under investigation, folkloristics has displayed a high degree of involvement by amateur and non-institutional researchers.

In the previous century, the field of folklore had already flourished under other names in Europe, as exemplified by figures like Johann Gottfried Herder and the Grimm Brothers (Briggs & Naithani 2012); the German word *volkskunde* and the French *arts et tradition populaire* refer to similar research areas. This divergence between continental Europe and Britain has had institutional ramifications, as the latter has been slow to accept folklore within the disciplinary bounds of ethnology, partly because of anthropology’s involvement in imperial and colonial enterprises (Rogan 2014b).

In Europe, folklore studies is often associated with ethnology or cultural anthropology, while in the U.S. the discipline is more independently institutionalized due to the country’s multi-ethnic composition and its lineages of Germanic and East European scholarship (Rogan 2014a). The mid-20th century struggles over folklore’s independence from ethnology or other fields led to intense institutional struggles throughout the 1960s, leading to the formation of the International Society for Ethnology and Folklore (Rogan 2014b).

The political nature of folkloristics has been evident from its inception, as its foundations were rooted in German romantic nationalism. The nationalist period of folkloristics was followed by and coincided with colonial tendencies in the field (Naithani 2015), and culminated in the full-blown appropriation of the discipline by Nazi Germany (Dow & Lixfeld 1994). Nationalist tendencies in the field are still visible in the countless ethnographic and folklore museums that still dot the tourism and heritage sector of Europe and elsewhere.

In the last few decades, the field has transformed significantly with a relatively belated postcolonial turn and a shift of gaze away from the non-modern. This transformation was led by various divergent tendencies including the flourishing of folkloristics in Eastern Europe and the United States. In Norway, for example, the fields of ethnology and folklore have converged as *kulturhistorie* (Oslo) and *kulturvitenskap* (Bergen), combining both intangible heritage and material culture (Rogan 2014a).

Established definitions of folklore are regularly challenged by technological change, particularly as new media reconfigure creative practices and networked communications blur the boundaries of ‘folk groups’ (Bronner 2016). Technological transformations have also opened up the field to new contexts—for example, industrial folklore (McLuhan 1951), office folklore (Preston, 1974), and scientific folklore (Schrempp, 1996). What these shifts have in common is the consistent movement of conceptualizing folklore not as a remnant of the past but rather as an ongoing process.

REFERENCES

- Briggs, Charles L., and Sadhana Naithani. 2012. “The Coloniality of Folklore: Towards a Multi-Generational Practice of Folkloristics.” *Studies in History* 28 (2): 231–70.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0257643013482404>.
- Bronner, Simon. J. 2016. “*Folklore: The Basics*”. Taylor & Francis.
- Dow, James. R., & Lixfeld, Hannjost. 1994. “*The Nazification of an Academic Discipline: Folklore in the Third Reich*”. Indiana University Press.
- Emrich, Duncan. 1946. “‘Folk-Lore’: William John Thoms.” *California Folklore Quarterly* 5 (4): 355.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1495929>
- McLuhan, Marshal. 1951. “*The mechanical bride: Folklore of industrial man*”. Vanguard Press.

Merton, Ambrose. 1846. "Folk-Lore." *The Athenæum*, August 22

Naithani, Sadhana. 2015. "*The story-time of the British Empire: Colonial and postcolonial folkloristics*". University Press of Mississippi.

Preston, Michael J. 1994. "Traditional Humor from the Fax Machine: 'All of a Kind.'" *Western Folklore* 53 (2): 147–69.
<https://doi.org/10.2307/1500101>.

Rogan, Bjarne. 2014a. "The Institutionalization of Folklore" In Regina Bendix (Ed.), *A companion to folklore* (Paperback ed, 598–630). Wiley-Blackwell.

Rogan, Bjarne. 2014b. "When the Folklorists Won the Battle but Lost the War: The Cumbersome (Re-) Birth of SIEF in 1964". *Cultural Analysis*, 13(1), 23–50.

Roper, Jonathan. 2007. "Thoms and the Unachieved 'Folk-Lore of England': TOPICS, NOTES AND COMMENTS." *Folklore* 118 (2): 203–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00155870701340035>.

Schrempp, Gregory. 1996. "Folklore and Science: Inflections of 'Folk' in Cognitive Research." *Journal of Folklore Research* 33 (3): 191–206.

FOLK THEORIES

Folk theories are causal frameworks, explanations and beliefs that people develop in order to explain, interpret and interact with complex processes, including the functioning of algorithmic systems.

In the 1990s, the concept of folk theory gained currency in social psychology and cognitive science, where it served to counter reductionist critiques of basic mental categories (Johnson-Laird and Oatley 1992). Folk theories, defined as “taken-for-granted categorizations and terminology that explain the physical, natural and chemical world and help orient actors” (Rip 2006, 349) have successively been identified across scientific disciplines and specialist domains. In their overview of the concept, Susan A. Gelman and Cristine H. Legare describe folk theories as adjacent to similar concepts like intuitive theories and naive theories, causal frameworks “that people construct to explain, interpret, and intervene in the world around them, including theories of mind, biology, or physics” (2011, 379).

From the mid-2010s, researchers in human-computer interaction (HCI) have also found in folk theories a useful conceptual apparatus to account for the processes behind the domestication of algorithms. When people start encountering computational processes such as the algorithmic curation of content in their everyday media use, they develop a range of informal responses including explanations and beliefs (Eslami et al. 2015) which are structurally similar to folklore. As Eslami and coauthors explain their terminological choice,

We take the prefix “folk” to be similar to its use in “folklore” in that a folk practice does not necessarily denote an individual view, but rather ideas that are developed, shared, and circulated by everyday people who are not expert (Eslami et al. 2016, 4).

These folk theories (or lack of them) not only impact user practices, but also contribute to shaping the algorithmic systems themselves, as user explanations and beliefs become incorporated in the feedback loops that turn the outputs of a system into new inputs (Rader and Gray 2015). Folk theories become more visible in times of friction – for example, when a platform implements changes to its algorithmic content curation and users respond with reactions that reveal detailed understandings of the system (DeVito et al. 2017, 9).

A growing body of scholarship traces how cultural contexts and sociotechnical infrastructures shape the development of folk theories of algorithms around the globe: Costa Rican users

imagine the algorithm of Swedish music streaming platform Spotify as either a demon-like being capable of possessing its user (Siles et al. 2020, 11), while German social media users, regardless of their technical literacy, draw consistent analogies that anthropomorphize social media algorithms (Dogruel 2021, 292).

Folk theories expand beyond algorithmic operations and into broader attributions of agency, as in the case of U.S. users of TikTok believing that social feeds result from algorithmic sorting aimed at making different social identities more or less visible according to prescribed values (Karizat et al. 2021, 21); similarly, Chinese gay men using the ambiguity of the Zhihu recommendation algorithm as both downranking gay-related Q&A threads while also unintentionally sheltering the gay community from other users of the same platform (Zhao 2023).

People also combine folk theories to articulate more generalized stances on algorithmic media, as in the case of the Norwegian respondents summarizing five folk theories into a broader affective state of “digital irritation” (Ytre-Arne and Moe 2021); these more generalized affects can in turn be explained with folk theorizations, as exemplified by dissatisfied Chinese social media users developing strategies to keep using unavoidable platforms in spite of their negative effects (Chen 2024). From its adoption, the concept of folk theory has proved to offer a useful paradigm to understand how non-experts make sense of complex systems through collectively shared intuitions, affects and practices.

REFERENCES

Chen, Keyi. 2024. “If It Is Bad, Why Don’t I Quit? Algorithmic Recommendation Use Strategy from Folk Theories.” *Global Media and China* 9 (3): 344–61.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/20594364231209354>.

DeVito, Michael A., Darren Gergle, and Jeremy Birnholtz. 2017. “‘Algorithms Ruin Everything’: #RIPTwitter, Folk Theories, and Resistance to Algorithmic Change in Social Media.” *Proceedings of the 2017 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 3163–74. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3025453.3025659>.

Dogruel, Leyla. 2021. “Folk Theories of Algorithmic Operations during Internet Use: A Mixed Methods Study.” *The Information Society* 37 (5): 287–98.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/01972243.2021.1949768>

Eslami, Motahhare, Karrie Karahalios, Christian Sandvig, et al. 2016. “First I ‘like’ It, Then I Hide It: Folk Theories of Social Feeds.”

Proceedings of the 2016 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 2371–82.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2858036.2858494>

Eslami, Motahhare, Aimee Rickman, Kristen Vaccaro, et al. 2015. “I Always Assumed That I Wasn’t Really That Close to [Her]”: Reasoning about Invisible Algorithms in News Feeds.”

Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems, 153–62.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702556>.

Gelman, Susan A., and Cristine H. Legare. 2011. “Concepts and Folk Theories.” *Annual Review of Anthropology* 40 (1): 379–98.

<https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-anthro-081309-145822>.

Johnson-Laird, P. N., and Keith Oatley. 1992. “Basic Emotions, Rationality, and Folk Theory.” *Cognition and Emotion* 6 (3–4): 201–

23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02699939208411069>.

Karizat, Nadia, Daniel Delmonaco, Motahhare Eslami, and Nazanin Andalibi. 2021. “Algorithmic Folk Theories and Identity: How TikTok Users Co-Produce Knowledge of Identity and Engage in Algorithmic Resistance.” *Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction* 5 (CSCW2): 1–44.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/3476046>

Kashima, Rader, Emilee, and Rebecca Gray. 2015.

“Understanding User Beliefs about Algorithmic Curation in the Facebook News Feed.” *Proceedings of the 33rd Annual ACM Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, 173–82.

<https://doi.org/10.1145/2702123.2702174>

Rip, Arie. 2006. “Folk Theories of Nanotechnologists.” *Science as Culture* 15 (4): 349–65.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/09505430601022676>.

Siles, Ignacio, Andrés Segura-Castillo, Ricardo Solís, and Mónica Sancho. 2020. “Folk Theories of Algorithmic Recommendations on Spotify: Enacting Data Assemblages in the Global South.” *Big Data & Society* 7 (1): 1–15.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/2053951720923377>.

Ytre-Arne, Brita, and Hallvard Moe. 2021. “Folk Theories of Algorithms: Understanding Digital Irritation.” *Media, Culture & Society* 43 (5): 807–24.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/0163443720972314>

Zhao, Longxuan. 2023. “Filter Bubbles? Also Protector Bubbles! Folk Theories of Zhihu Algorithms among Chinese Gay Men.”

Social Media + Society 9 (2): 1–10.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/20563051231168647>

LORE

Lore originally referred to religious doctrine or other forms of learned knowledge, and was eventually incorporated into the 19th century definition of folklore; in the twenty-first century, it has been reclaimed to describe the bodies of knowledge that form around fandoms, fictional worlds and online social contexts.

The term lore comes from the Old English *lār*, indicating that which is taught or learned – knowledge, science or doctrine. Originally used with a strictly religious meaning around the 10th century, the definition of lore expanded to other forms of knowledge; in Chaucer’s *The Canterbury Tales* (1387-1400), the word is recurrently used to indicate wisdom and learning (“the wisest was of lore”, “learned in his lore”). From this general use, lore then shifted towards indicating bodies of knowledge correlated to a specific subject, such as “animal lore” or “fairy lore” (Tréguer 2017). In a 1846 letter to British literary magazine *The Athenæum*, antiquary and writer William John Thoms (writing under the pseudonym of Ambrose Merton), argued for the need to rename the field of popular literature or popular antiquities (dedicated to “the manners, customs, observances, superstitions, ballads, proverbs, &c., of the olden time”) by using what he presented as “a good Saxon compound, Folk-Lore,—the Lore of the People” (Merton 1846, 862c). As Duncan Emrich argues in the centenary of this coinage, Thoms’ linguistic invention was a success that went well beyond the magazine:

The "Folk-Lore" columns in *The Athenæum* continued to be published with considerable regularity from August, 1846, until November, 1849. In them Thoms made his initial great contributions to the field as we now know it. He employed the word "folk-lore" for the first time and, with the weight of the powerful *Athenæum* behind him, saw it adopted by correspondent and receive general circulation in England. He encouraged the collection and preservation of folklore materials. (1946, 364) Only a few decades later, Thoms’ “folk-lore” had become a broad field of research with dedicated journals and societies, encompassing the study of narratives, customs, beliefs and forms of speech, with proponents arguing for its academic legitimacy as “the science which treats of the survivals of archaic beliefs and customs” (Gomme 1885, 14).

For more than a century, folklore became the most common occurrence of the term lore, widely surpassing it in popularity. It is only in the early 2000s that lore has seen a resurgence in the realms of gaming, fandom and transmedia storytelling, where it

has been increasingly used to describe bodies of knowledge that accrue around celebrities, fictional characters, intellectual properties and the worlds in which they are set (Krzywinska 2008). More generally, lore has become a key concept in internet culture, as it accurately captures the kinds of knowledge that form around specific online communities, content or practices (Dingsun & Marrs 2021). When confronted with the scale and complexity of the internet, users develop ways of interfacing with information that reflect the emerging “lore dynamics” of the medium, and engaging with lore becomes “an ongoing and participatory act, unfolding stories without ossifying them” (Marrs & Dingsun 2021). In 2024, ‘lore’ was shortlisted for the Oxford Word of the Year, testifying to the newfound popularity of the term; on social media platforms like TikTok, lore has become a pervasive keyword through which users mythologize experiences and life stories, share knowledge about historical events, and build community around identities and social roles (Smith 2025).

REFERENCES:

- Dingsun, Tiger, and Libby Marrs. 2021. “Introduction: 9999.” *Other Internet*. <https://otherinter.net/research/lore/9999/>.
- Emrich, Duncan. 1946. “‘Folk-Lore’: William John Thoms.” *California Folklore Quarterly* 5 (4): 355. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1495929>.
- Gomme, George Laurence. 1885. “The Science of Folk-Lore.” *The Folk-Lore Journal* 3 (1): 1–16.
- Krzywinska, Tanya. 2008. “World Creation and Lore: World of Warcraft as Rich Text.” In *Digital Culture, Play, and Identity: A World of Warcraft Reader*, edited by Hilde G. Corneliussen and Jill Walker Rettberg. MIT Press.
- Marrs, Libby, and Tiger Dingsun. 2021. “How to Read the Internet.” *Other Internet*. <https://otherinter.net/research/lore/how-to-read-the-internet/>.
- Merton, Ambrose. 1846. “Folk-Lore.” *The Athenæum*, August 22.
- Smith, Kate McNicholas. 2025. “The Lore of ‘Lore’ – How Fandoms Created an Online Phenomenon from an Old English Word.” *The Conversation*, March 31. <https://doi.org/10.64628/AB.3ev6vksm4>.
- Tréguer, Pascal. 2017. “The Creation of the Word ‘Folklore.’” *Word Histories*, November 24. <https://wordhistories.net/2017/11/24/origin-of-folklore/>.

#Looks like you're
trying to circumvent
human creativity |

#Looks like you're
trying to circumvent
human creativity |

#Looks like you're
trying to circumvent
human creativity |

PROMPT WRITING

Prompt writing refers to the iterative practice of composing instructions for large language models in order to guide, refine, and customize their outputs.

Etymologically, the word prompt is derived from the Latin *promere*, meaning "to bring forth", which in the 1600s came to be used to refer to the theatrical practice of assisting a speaker with lines (Merriam-Webster 2026). In computer programming the term has been used to refer to a message or character displayed by a computer directing the user to respond, ever since the earliest IBM time-sharing computer systems in the 1960s (IBM 1966). With the arrival of large language models (LLMs), the term has been adapted to refer to a set of instructions given to a large language model to customize its output (Radford et al. 2019; White et al. 2023; Shen et al. 2024). These instructions are often written in conventional language and is understood as a form of programming. By providing context, guidelines, or rules for the subsequent interaction, prompts can enhance LLM output by customising or refining its capabilities (White and Fu et al. 2023). A good prompt will “bias the model towards generating desired outputs” (Zamfirescu-Pereira et al. 2023), thus improving the answers provided by the model.

Since prompts are necessary to interact effectively with LLMs, the ability to write effective prompts has been identified as an essential aspect of AI literacy (Knoth et al. 2024). Prompts can be written in conventional language, which reduces the technical barriers to entry (White et al. 2023; Schneider, Haag, and Kruse 2023; Lo 2024). However, crafting an effective prompt is not trivial, and requires experimentation, experience, and continual refinement. As a result “prompt engineering” has become a specialised skill and productive research domain in computer science, and an established aspect of AI literacy (Gupta and Shivers-McNair 2024).

As large language models with chat interfaces have become available to the public, social media has become host to a proliferation of posts and dedicated communities featuring lay people’s experiments with prompting (Zamfirescu-Pereira et al. 2023; Shen et al. 2024). Goloujeh and Sullivan argues that prompt engineering is “a socio-cultural practice shaped by collective knowledge building” (Goloujeh, Sullivan, and Magerko 2024, 1). The existence of practices such as 'prompt jamming' and collectively sourced prompt databases emphasise the collaborative and social aspects of prompt creation (Goloujeh et al. 2024). An illustrative example of this are the communities

dedicated to “jailbreaking” LLMs, in which users share techniques and tips for designing prompts in the aim of bypassing the guardrails imposed on the commercial models (Shen and Chen et al. 2024). The art of prompting is also a central topic in communities dedicated to synthetic media such as AI-generated images, in which prompts are often conceptualized as part of the artwork (Chang et al. 2023). In these communities the creative exploration of the model itself are an intrinsic part of the practice, often motivated by fun, creative self-expression, and interest in exploring new technologies (Oppenlaender et al. 2024, Oppenlaender 2024). The prompts shared in online communities can also be seen as a type of algorithmic folklore, as expressions of a vernacular culture seeking to develop ways of relating to and making use of AI technologies (Gunderson 2025).

The professionalism and instrumentalism implied by “prompt engineering” makes it a poor term to describe these exploratory, community-led, often artistic or playful practices. The use of the term “engineering” to describe this activity has been criticized by Selber who argues that “prompting is principally a writing activity that has been appropriated by the discourse of engineering” (2024, 11). Gupta and Shivers-McNair argues that “prompt writing” would be a better descriptor, emphasizing the “iterative, rhetorical process” (2024, 2) of the practice.

REFERENCES

- Chang, Minsuk, Stefania Druga, Alexander J. Fiannaca, et al. 2023. “The Prompt Artists.” *Creativity and Cognition*, June 19, 75–87. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3591196.3593515>
- Chen, Banghao, Zhaofeng Zhang, Nicolas Langrené, and Shengxin Zhu. 2024. “Unleashing the Potential of Prompt Engineering in Large Language Models: A Comprehensive Review.” arXiv:2310.14735. Preprint, arXiv, September 5. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2310.14735>
- Goloujeh, Atefeh Mahdavi, Anne Sullivan, and Brian Magerko. 2024. “The Social Construction of Generative AI Prompts.” *Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, May 2, 1–7. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613905.3650947>.
- Gunderson, Marianne. 2026. “DON’T WORRY ABOUT FORMALITIES: PROMPTING AS ALGORITHMIC FOLKLORE.” *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research*, ahead of print, January 2. <https://doi.org/10.5210/spir.v2024i0.15165>

- Gupta, Anuj, and Ann Shivers-McNair. 2024. “‘Wayfinding’ through the AI Wilderness: Mapping Rhetorics of ChatGPT Prompt Writing on X (Formerly Twitter) to Promote Critical AI Literacies.” *Computers and Composition* 74 (December): 102882. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compcom.2024.102882>
- Knoth, Nils, Antonia Tolzin, Andreas Janson, and Jan Marco Leimeister. 2024. “AI Literacy and Its Implications for Prompt Engineering Strategies.” *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 6 (June): 100225. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2024.100225>
- Lo, Leo S. 2023. “The Art and Science of Prompt Engineering: A New Literacy in the Information Age.” *Internet Reference Services Quarterly* 27 (4): 203–10. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10875301.2023.2227621>
- Oppenlaender, Jonas. 2024. “The Cultivated Practices of Text-to-Image Generation.” In *Humane Autonomous Technology*, edited by Rebekah Rousi, Catharina Von Koskull, and Virpi Roto. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-66528-8_14
- Oppenlaender, Jonas, Rhema Linder, and Johanna Silvennoinen. 2024. “Prompting AI Art: An Investigation into the Creative Skill of Prompt Engineering.” *International Journal of Human–Computer Interaction*, November 28, 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10447318.2024.2431761>
- Sanchez, Téó. 2023. “Examining the Text-to-Image Community of Practice: Why and How Do People Prompt Generative AIs?” *Creativity and Cognition*, June 19, 43–61. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3591196.3593051>
- Selber, Stuart A. 2024. “Artificial Intelligence and the Intellectual Legacy of Johndan Johnson-Eilola.” *Programmatic Perspectives* 15 (1): 11–19.
- Shen, Xinyue, Zeyuan Chen, Michael Backes, Yun Shen, and Yang Zhang. 2024. “‘Do Anything Now’: Characterizing and Evaluating In-The-Wild Jailbreak Prompts on Large Language Models.” *Proceedings of the 2024 on ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security*, December 2, 1671–85. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3658644.3670388>
- White, Jules, Quchen Fu, Sam Hays, et al. 2023. “A Prompt Pattern Catalog to Enhance Prompt Engineering with ChatGPT.” arXiv:2302.11382. Preprint, arXiv, February 21. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2302.11382>.

PLASTICITY

From Greek plastikos (molded) and Latin plasticus (altered, formed) Plasticity refers to the malleability of neurons to rewire itself and expand their network.

Malabou—who introduced the concept from the discipline of neuroscience—though the notion existed in art history and philosophy—in particular to philosophy defines it as follows, she also interrogates the positive neoliberal ideas that have appropriated the concept using it to mean resilience and renewal. Instead, she focuses also on destructive plasticity i.e. the kind that causes rupture building on the French word: *plastiquage*—which carries the double meaning of both the characteristic of something plastic and bomb or explosive (Nunes 2026). Some read her work in a maximal way by interrogating space and time's plasticity. That kind of reading that also opens up Hegel's notion of the *aufhebung* where sublation includes dissolution and also a rupture (Clemens 2010; Nunes 2026).

“Plastic material retains an imprint and thereby resists endless polymorphism” (Vahanian 2008)

By focusing on—destructive plasticity—which moves the focus away from positive notions such as flexibility, adaptability and so on. Her work is of importance because continental philosophers in particular psychoanalysts have not reckoned with the revolutions in brain science and its consequences (Vahanian 2008). Malabou pushes forth Hegel's work by providing reading which presents Hegel's work with a forward momentum.

Opposed to elasticity, plasticity offers a way to grasp self-organisation. As she explicitly positions it against a “program” (Malabou 2022), she extends the decentralised self-organization of neurons beyond the brain and the subject to post-industrial capitalist society. Because of the incessant suspicion of neuroscience, Malabou's rehabilitation of the discipline requires long detours through a critique of capitalism as well as centralised planning ala USSR. By the end, the capitalist society's adaptability starts to mirror neuronal adaptations.

Plasticity remains an important concern to grasp because of its endless polymorphism; Though her concept situates the social in a post-industrial age it's worth remembering that she avoids a strong historicism. “This is the case is no less biological than it is spiritual (or mental), it is no less material than it is historical. That is, the subject is not merely and ineluctably the social-historical-economic construct of an age.” (Vahanian 2008).

She claims that capitalistic society mirrors the neuronal organisation of the brain, and that the brain mirrors capitalist society in that both are de-centralised and highly adaptable.

To grasp what Artificial intelligence is entails thinking through at the intersection with plasticity, especially instances such as brainrot, dopamine drip, etc. provide a viable entry point. More broadly the convergence is explicit as “Daniel Dennett shows that a computer may be said to be plastic” (Vahanian 2008).

REFERENCES

Clemens, Justin. 2010. ‘The Age of Plastic; or, Catherine Malabou on the Hegelian Futures Market’. *Cosmos and History: The Journal of Natural and Social Philosophy* 6 (1): 153–63.

Malabou, Catherine. 2022. *What Should We Do with Our Brain?* With Marc Jeannerod. Perspectives in Continental Philosophy. Fordham University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.1515/9780823293520>

Nunes, Beatriz. 2026. ‘Plastic Scenes: Images from the Future’. *Interdisciplinary Science Reviews*, January 13, 03080188251407996.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/03080188251407996>

Vahanian, Noëlle. 2008. ‘A Conversation with Catherine Malabou’. *Journal for Cultural and Religious Theory* 9 (1): 1–13.

SYNTHETIC MEDIA

Synthetic media refers to any kind of original content (text, image, audio, video, etc.) that is partially or entirely generated by deep learning models without the need of human input or intervention.

The late 2010s witnessed the emergence of a new kind of digital content: media generated through deep learning. This kind of content rapidly scaled up from being an experimental niche in computer science research to popular culture, following the diffusion of machine learning advancements including generative adversarial networks (GANs), variational autoencoders (VAEs), and transformer models. These innovations, enabling the automated production of original text, speech and images without human intervention or supervision, have enabled the consolidation of generative artificial intelligence as a major application of machine learning.

The paradigmatic example of AI-generated content entering popular culture dates back to 2017, with the appearance of deepfakes - images and videos in which deep learning is used to swap or animate human faces. Other widely discussed cases, including the GAN-based "This Person Does Not Exist" website, the virtual influencer Lil Miquela, and the first AI-generated painting sold at a Christie's auction for \$432,500, explain the need for a new term capable of encompassing these kinds of content. While colloquial terms like 'deepfake' indicate specific genres and techniques, 'synthetic media' has been used since the late 2010s as the expert term of choice to indicate a new category of human-like, textual and audiovisual content produced by deep learning models (Millière 2022)

While machines and computers have been capable of producing outputs autonomously long before the advent of deep learning, the use of synthetic media responds to a need to identify and describe a new category of content characterized by automated and unsupervised generation, originality, reduced need for human input, and difficulty of detection. The choice of the 'synthetic' adjective is not surprising: in philosophy, synthesis is the combination of two or more elements into an original creation; in biology, a synthetic medium indicates a formulation of which all chemical components are known; both lab-grown embryos and androids are described as synthetic humans; and synthesis is a common technique in music and speech generation. While competing terms such as 'generative media' or 'AI-generated content' coexist alongside it, the adoption of the category of synthetic media by both experts and the tech industry points to its consolidation as the category of choice.

Because of its realism and ease of creation, synthetic media pose a challenge to epistemic practices grounded on verification, and their dissemination can contribute to the spread of misinformation and erode trust in established communication channels such as the web (Lu et al. 2022) while also flooding social media (Corsi et al. 2024). As a relatively new phenomenon, the spread of synthetic media has been mostly analyzed from three key perspectives in academic literature: methods for detecting it, malicious applications, and potential benefits (Roe et al. 2024). Beyond its use in entertainment, misinformation and art, synthetic media can also be used as synthetic data, contributing to the expansion of the capabilities of machine learning models for uses beyond the generation of content, such as algorithmic decision-making and surveillance (Martin & Newell 2024).

REFERENCES

- Corsi, Giulio, Bill Marino, and Willow Wong. 2024. "The Spread of Synthetic Media on X." *Harvard Kennedy School Misinformation Review*, no. 3, 1–19.
- Lu, Huimin, Xing Xu, Jože Guna, and Gautam Srivastava. 2022. "Special Issue on Synthetic Media on the Web." *World Wide Web* 25 (4): 1517–18.
- Martin, Aaron, and Bryce Newell. 2024. "Synthetic Data, Synthetic Media, and Surveillance." *Surveillance & Society* 22 (4): 448–52.
- Millière, Raphaël. 2022. "Deep Learning and Synthetic Media." *Synthese* 200 (3): 231.
- Roe, Jasper, Mike Perkins, and Leon Furze. 2024. "Deepfakes and Higher Education: A Research Agenda and Scoping Review of Synthetic Media." *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice* 21 (10).

SURVEILLANCE

Surveillance refers to the systematic tracking, collecting and analysing information of individuals and populations either physically or digitally to obtain power over them, and also to generate profit.

Despite surveillance referring to physical, occasional, and local monitoring of individuals or groups in the 20th century, the definition has shifted with the integration and widespread use of digital technologies. Foucault (1979), in his book *Discipline & Punish*, describes the Panopticon –a watchtower within a prison conceptualized by Jeremy Bentham in the late 18th century– as a structure that allows a single watcher to observe everything at once, and thereby leading to an autonomous behavioral modification of those being watched even without a constant guard present. As the prisoners internalize the perception of an all-seeing authority, they adjust their action to be more socially appropriate. Lyon (2011) considers this as a good example of omniscient gaze, where the watcher is invisible to the general public but the ordinary people live and adjust their behaviour with the consideration as such a watcher exists. With adoption of digital technologies, surveillance became less about direct observation, and more an embedded condition of everyday life, operating through digital platforms, application interfaces, and data-driven processes (Lyon 2007); where the data is utilized for *social sorting*: to classify data in a way to treat people –users– differently. Lyon’s description of surveillance also feeds Zuboff’s (2019) concept of surveillance capitalism, where private information that we decide to share or are extracted through our digital habits are used as means to establish structural power to drive social change, and to generate profit through the social change and prediction of behavior. In lighter terms, Zuboff explains that:

Surveillance capitalism unilaterally claims human experience as free raw material for translation into behavioral data. Although some of these data are applied to product or service improvement, the rest are declared as a proprietary behavioral surplus, fed into advanced manufacturing processes known as “machine intelligence,” and fabricated into prediction products that anticipate what you will do now, soon, and later. [...] At its core, surveillance capitalism is parasitic and self-referential. It revives Karl Marx’s old image of capitalism as a vampire that feeds on labor, but with an unexpected turn. Instead of labor, surveillance capitalism feeds on

every aspect of every human's experience (Zuboff 2019, 4).

Surveillance has become something less about physical watching and more about algorithmic tracking. Unlike classical surveillance paradigms, algorithmic surveillance often functions without continuous human oversight or the idea of a human watcher (contrasting the concept of the human watcher of panopticon). It depends on extracting data from users of social networking platforms and mobile applications, among other algorithmically mediated networks, and to estimate our behaviour based on our previously established patterns. With these developments that are driven by opaque algorithms, users of these platforms generate speculative explanations, and ritualized practices to make sense of how systems behave (Bucher 2016). Beliefs about what gets recommended, how devices ongoingly eavesdrop to conversations are narrations about surveillance functions, which shape user behavior and imagination.

REFERENCES

Bucher, Taina. 2016. "The Algorithmic Imaginary: Exploring the Ordinary Affects of Facebook Algorithms." *Information, Communication & Society* 20 (1): 30–44.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2016.1154086>.

Foucault, Michel. 1979. "Discipline and punish: The birth of the prison". Trans A. Sheridan. Vintage.

Lyon, David. 2007. "Surveillance, Security and Social Sorting: Emerging Research Priorities." *International Criminal Justice Review* 17 (3): 161–70.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/1057567707306643>.

Lyon, David. 2011." *David Lyon - Surveillance Cultures, September 2011*". Youtube:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kWd-IRlvJU4>

Zuboff, Shoshana. 2019. "The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power". Profile Books, London.

SURVEILLANCE CULTURE

Surveillance culture encompasses the norms, practices and narratives about how the embeddedness of surveillance is normalized and reproduced in everyday life, shifting the attention from surveillance as a top-down system of control to surveillance as a cultural condition shaped by everyday interactions with and through digital platforms and algorithms.

The concept of surveillance culture emerged in the early 21st century, due to a number of circumstances including the widespread adoption and speed of the Internet, 9/11 terror attack, innovations on the technological and digital fronts, mainly introduction of smart devices, and digital platforms (Gelfgren et al. 2023). Culture of surveillance succeeds that of the surveillance in Panopticon. While panoptic power occupied “a system of visibility in which the observed are aware of being monitored” (Schleusener 2019, 179), in the post-panopticon surveillance, the all-authoritative watcher is replaced by a hidden, semi-reflexive, and public gaze (Schleusener 2019) where the power of the watcher is replaced by algorithmic systems and the wider population.. The public gaze leads to a participatory culture of surveillance where maintaining a refined online persona becomes a part of everyday life, despite the platforms keeping a track on numerous streams of data transferred to them (Lyon 2018).

Users voluntarily disclose their private data in exchange for personalization (i.e. workout planning mobile applications), for connectivity (i.e. social media platforms like Facebook, BeReal, etc.), or for security (i.e. baby monitors and applications tracking breastfeeding/diaper change frequency); which makes surveillance a participatory practice. As Shoshana Zuboff also discusses, this dynamic blurs the line of consent and coercion (2019), and makes surveillance seem less of an institutional practice and more of a cultural practice, despite it being mainly an institutional control system.

As a response to these developments, David Lyon (2018) argues that the way we understand and practice surveillance has shifted from business domains to our everyday life. We can now *search* for any ordinary person to gather personal and private information about them, their contact details and at least a photo are usually the first to appear in the search results. Every digital footprint leaves a trace, and any ordinary person can

access information about one another through the data we voluntarily provide to social media platforms, or through data our smart devices collect about us (i.e. location). Surveillance moves away from being something that happens to ordinary people, and is replaced by a concept that covers initiation by ordinary people themselves - in the words of David Lyon:

Exploring today's surveillance culture through the lenses of imaginaries and practices offers fresh ways of thinking about surveillance in general. It opens up a much more complex cultural landscape than can be captured with the concepts of surveillance state or surveillance society – though it does not supersede them – and simultaneously takes us beyond simple conceptual binaries such as power–participation, in/visibility, privacy–publicness or even the misleading us-and-them of much popular surveillance rhetoric (Lyon 2018, 43).

Supporting Lyon's post-industrial idea of surveillance (2018), Anderson and Rainie's prophetic report on how digital life would be like in the year 2025 estimated that only the well-educated and well-funded small group will know how to maintain their privacy on digital platforms (2014). However, this report is proven to be optimistic as communication technologies became more disruptive, interfering with the private life of individuals. In 2010, the former CEO of Alphabet INC, the holding group that also houses Google, Eric Schmidt has stated "we don't need you to type it all because we know where you are with your permission, we know where you've been with your permission, we can more or less guess what you are thinking about." (Eric Schmidt 2010, 16:40:00) speaking about how the algorithms of social networking platforms cooperate to collect data about an individual's habits, whereabouts, social connections, and preferences, leading to a holistic profile of the individual which individuals themselves give the permission to. This illustrates that surveillance culture has become an embedded aspect of our everyday life; through algorithms where they determine who we are and what we like through the information they have collected about us.

REFERENCES

Anderson, Janna, and Lee Rainie. 2014. "Digital Life in 2025." *Pew Research Center*, March 11.
<https://www.pewresearch.org/internet/2014/03/11/digital-life-in-2025/>.

Gelfgren, Stefan., Cocq, Coppélie., Samuelsson, Lars., & Enbom, Jesper. 2023. "Introduction: The complex web of everyday surveillance"

Lyon, David. 2018. "The culture of surveillance: Watching as a way of life". John Wiley & Sons.

Schmidt, Eric. 2010. Eric Schmidt Remarks: Google CEO Eric Schmidt talked about technology's impact on all aspects of life and what's the next step for Google. James Bennet, Atlantic magazine's editor, moderated [Video]. C-SPAN. <https://www.c-span.org/program/public-affairs-event/eric-schmidt-remarks/234317>

Schleusener, Simon. 2019. "The surveillance nexus: Digital culture and the society of control". REAL: Yearbook of Research in English and American Literature.

Zuboff, Shoshana. 2019. "The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Age of Surveillance Capitalism: The Fight for a Human Future at the New Frontier of Power". Profile Books, London.

TECHNOSPHERE

The technosphere is a geological perspective that indicates a new paradigm and epoch of earth history where the role of technology is considered a large-scale, earth-changing phenomenon similar to the lithosphere.

Human interference and exploitation of the biosphere has had massive ramifications of earth functions and environments. In an effort to emphasize the role of mankind the term 'Anthropocene', combining the Greek terminology *anthropos* [human] and *-cene* [new], was created to indicate a new geological epoch (Crutzen and Stoermer 2000). This view of humankind as a geological force in and of itself has become a widely shared belief. The technosphere, however, proposes a supporting perspective onto the anthropocene, shifting the sole emphasis on human action by highlighting the role of technology itself as an autonomous actor, and mankind as (essential) component that society has become dependent on (Haff 2014b).

The technosphere is a concept introduced and developed by American geologist and engineer Peter Haff (2012; 2014a; 2014b). The geological perspective focuses on the large-scale transport processes of solid material, fossil fuel and other energy resources, where previous epochs only had biological systems that were able to perform similar function on a much smaller scale (with some exceptions like river-sediment in large streams). With the added element of human purpose and agency, the technosphere goes beyond physics, including "[...]power, communication, industrial, governmental, military, and other widely distributed and interconnected technological systems on whose function modern civilisation and society is based." (Haff 2012, 149). Yet, Haff argues, humans are only parts of a larger puzzle- "[...] even if they are people, does not by itself distinguish it from other geological paradigms" (Haff 2014a, 306). This stance has been met with debate, criticising the naturalising of labour and trashmaking, ignoring the political violence within (Zahara 2016). In his book *Shrinking the Technosphere: Getting a Grip on Technologies That Limit Our Autonomy, Self-Sufficiency and Freedom*, Orlov proposes the technosphere as the antithesis of the biosphere, becoming an entity that transforms and replaces nature - irreversibly subjugating humankind to its whims (2016). This shows an alternative emphasis on the human relation and effect to technology contrary to Haff's; subjugating force over energy transfer. As Zahara says:

Autonomous or not, the technosphere produces waste.
We readily see this in exhaust from factories, fertilizer

runoff, and radiation from nuclear waste. A technosphere must expel harmful matter from its structure and processes in order to maintain its functionality. Crucially, the technosphere is predicated upon an understanding that the problem with certain wastes (including people) is not necessarily the system itself, but that people—for reasons outside of the technosphere’s function or responsibility—are made external to capitalist modes of production. (Zahara 2016).

At the core of the technosphere lies current and emerging theories of technology’s role in transforming humankind, energy sources and the environment. Climate change and other consequences of technology and mankind continue to escalate, and current debates surrounding the massive energy consumption performed by data centres must be seen as a continuation to this debate. As more energy and resources are put into the algorithmic transformation of society and the ecosystem, discussions provoked by the technosphere have more room to grow.

REFERENCES

- Crutzen, Paul J., and Eugene F. Stoermer. 2021. «The ‘Anthropocene’ (2000)». In Paul J. Crutzen and the Anthropocene: A New Epoch in Earth’s History, edited by Susanne Benner, Gregor Lax, Paul J. Crutzen, Ulrich Pöschl, Jos Lelieveld, and Hans Günter Brauch. Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-82202-6_2
- Haff, P. K. 2012. «Technology and Human Purpose: The Problem of Solids Transport on the Earth’s Surface». *Earth System Dynamics* 3 (2): 149–56. <https://doi.org/10.5194/esd-3-149-2012>
- Haff, Peter. 2014. «Humans and Technology in the Anthropocene: Six Rules». *The Anthropocene Review* 1 (2): 126–36. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2053019614530575>
- Haff, Peter. K. 2014a. «Technology as a geological phenomenon: implications for human well-being». *Geological Society, London, Special Publications* 395 (1): 301–9. <https://doi.org/10.1144/SP395.4>
- Orlov, Dmitry. 2016. “Shrinking the Technosphere: Getting a Grip on Technologies That Limit Our Autonomy, Self-Sufficiency and Freedom.” *New Society Publishers*, Limited.
- Zahara, Alex. 2016. «Anthropocene Adjustments: Discarding the Technosphere». *Discard Studies*, may 26. <https://discardstudies.com/2016/05/26/anthropocene-adjustments-discarding-the-technosphere/>

VERNACULAR

Vernacular commonly indicates a local, ordinary, and unofficial spoken language, but it has also been used to describe other kinds of cultural production that are opposed to formal or institutional structures.

The term 'vernacular' comes from the Latin *verna*, a word of possibly Etruscan origin which in ancient Roman times indicated a slave born in the house (rather than a foreign one bought or captured abroad). Its diminutive *vernaculus* was used as a figurative way to mean 'native', and Latin grammars listed local terms, as opposed to foreign words, as *vocabula vernacula*. In the 14th century, Dante Alighieri argued for the use of the 'vulgar' vernacular language over Latin, which had become the lingua franca of Europe: "Of these two kinds of language, the more noble is the vernacular: first, because it was the language originally used by the human race; second, because the whole world employs it [...]; and third because it is natural to us" (Alighieri 1305). While Dante was among the first authors to articulate this opposition in Europe, the transition to vernacular languages happened at different points in history around the world - as early as the 12th century in India, with the Bhakti [devotion] movement which translated Sanskrit texts to local languages; as recently as the 1920s in China, when classical language was replaced by written vernacular Chinese (*baihua*) during the May Fourth movement. When the term vernacular entered the English vocabulary in the 17th century, it referred to local languages spoken in geographical areas (Mair 2023).

In modern linguistics, vernacular is used to define spoken languages that are informal, ordinary, and perceived as of lower social status than standard or official languages - for example, AAVE (African American Vernacular English). But the use of this term transcends linguistics. In 1960, anthropologist Margaret Lantis adopted the adjective to define "vernacular culture" as all kinds of speech acts that are different from literary or journalistic language (1960, 202-203), a definition that echoes the structural opposition between official and unofficial speech already formalized by Dante. Henry Jenkins has further developed this definition of vernacular culture for the realms of popular culture and fandom by arguing that practices like "textual poaching" allow television spectators to create a participatory culture out of materials coming from mass media (1992). Jenkins defines vernacular culture as "culture that is generated by amateurs, a term intended to suggest the parallels between folk culture and fan culture" (2006, 293), echoing Lantis' framing and connecting it to the kinds of folklore produced by amateur creators: "Like the

older folk culture of quilting bees and barn dances, this new vernacular culture encourages broad participation, grassroots creativity, and a bartering or gift economy" (2006, 132). In recent years, as Ülo Valk argues, vernacular has become "one of the key words in contemporary folkloristics and a useful tool in studying several areas of culture, such as narrative and local knowledge" (2022). By extending its meanings of local, native, ordinary, unofficial, stigmatized and even anti-institutional language to other domains, the term vernacular has been used to describe various domains of cultural production, ranging from vernacular architecture, vernacular criticism and vernacular photography to vernacular theories, knowledges and beliefs.

REFERENCES

- Alighieri, Dante. 1305. *De Vulgari Eloquentia* [On the Eloquence of the Vernacular].
- Jenkins, Henry. 1992. *Textual Poachers: Television Fans & Participatory Culture*. *Studies in Culture and Communication*. New York, NY: Routledge.
- Jenkins, Henry. 2006. *Convergence Culture: Where Old and New Media Collide*. New York, NY: New York University Press.
- Lantis, Margaret. 1960. "Vernacular Culture." *American Anthropologist* 62 (2): 202–16.
- Valk, Ülo. 2022. "An Introduction to Vernacular Knowledge." In *Vernacular Knowledge: Contesting Authority, Expressing Beliefs*, edited by Ülo Valk and Marion Bowman, 1–21. Sheffield, United Kingdom: Equinox Publishing.

VERNACULAR CREATIVITY

Vernacular creativity describes the creative practices behind everyday, ordinary, mundane cultural production, which both predate new media technologies and are shaped by them, bridging the gap between amateur and professional, personal and commercial, local and global.

The concept of “vernacular creativity” was formulated in the mid-2000s by Jean Burgess, who defines it as a variety of “creative practices that emerge from highly particular and non-elite social contexts and communicative conventions, mediated and transformed when brought into relationship with digital distribution, consumption and network technologies” (2005). Burgess draws on the use of ‘vernacular’ in cultural studies, and directly patterns her concept on similar ones such as ‘vernacular speech’, ‘vernacular architecture’, and ‘vernacular photography’, emphasizing its linkage to ordinary, mundane, and everyday cultural production. In her work, vernacular creativity is directly connected to digital technologies, as grassroots practices converge with “emerging neoliberal business and economic models under which consumers (or ‘users’), particularly of technology, are considered to possess and exercise more creativity and agency than before” (2006, 202). For Burgess, vernacular creativity is also not defined in opposition to commercial or professional forms of cultural production, but closely tied with mass media and popular culture (2007, 33).

The coinage of vernacular creativity reflects a broader uptake of the adjective ‘vernacular’ across disciplinary contexts, where it helps make sense of phenomena emerging in postmodern and postcolonial contexts. For example, anthropological discussions of “vernacular cosmopolitanisms” (Werbner 2008) foreground the paradoxical coexistence of local specificities and global modernity, and recognize the potential flourishing of “vernacular democratic creativity” (Graeber 2008). In human geography, the concept underpins the definition of “spaces of vernacular creativity” (Edensor et al. 2010) which in turn undermine and expand restrictive neoliberal theorizations of the ‘creative city’ and the ‘creative class’. Similarly to Burgess, this approach emphasizes mundanity, ordinariness and everydayness:

Vernacular creativity foregrounds the un-hip, the un-cool, and possibly the downright square, and embraces those marginal and non-glamorous creative practices excluded

from arts- and culture-based regeneration. Vernacular forms of creativity are neither extraordinary nor spectacular [...], but are part of a range of mundane, intensely social practices grounded in a variety of everyday practices and places [...]. (Edensor et al. 2010, 10)

While this focus privileges practices outside of profit and productivity, researchers also recognize how consumers also develop vernacular creative practices to question, resist and criticize corporate and commercial narratives (Brownlie & Hewer 2011).

As Jean Burgess notes, vernacular creativity encompasses “a range of mundane but intensely social forms and practices – from scrapbooking to family photography and the storytelling that forms part of casual chat” (2010, 116) which predate digital media; at the same time, these practices are being profoundly reshaped by the increasing central role of digital technologies in everyday life. Linguists recognize how new technologies such as social media platforms are changing everyday practices like reading and writing, leading to new “vernacular literacies” that challenge the distinction between official and unofficial, global and local (Barton & Lee 2012). Similarly, media scholars identify vernacular creativity behind the creation and circulation of internet memes (Milner 2013), and argue that new digital creative practices are blurring the boundaries between art and user-generated content (Literat 2017). When revisiting their spatial theorization of vernacular creativity, Tim Edensor and Steve Millington acknowledge that this blurring of boundaries also complicates other assumed binaries including those of commercial and the personal, professional and amateur, urban and rural (2018).

REFERENCES

Barton, David, and Carmen K. M. Lee. 2012. “Redefining Vernacular Literacies in the Age of Web 2.0.” *Applied Linguistics* 33 (3): 282–98. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/ams009>.

Brownlie, Douglas, and Paul Hewer. 2011. “Articulating Consumers through Practices of Vernacular Creativity.” *Scandinavian Journal of Management* 27 (2): 243–53. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scaman.2011.03.003>.

Burgess, Jean. 2005. “Mapping Vernacular Creativity v. 0.1.” *Creativity/Machine*, March 26. <http://hypertext.rmit.edu.au:80/~burgess/2005/03/26/mapping-vernacular-creativity-v-01/>.

Burgess, Jean. 2006. "Hearing Ordinary Voices: Cultural Studies, Vernacular Creativity and Digital Storytelling." *Continuum: Journal of Media & Cultural Studies* 20 (2): 201–14.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/10304310600641737>.

Burgess, Jean. 2007. "Vernacular Creativity and New Media." PhD Thesis, Queensland University of Technology.
eprints.qut.edu.au/16378/1/Jean_Burgess_Thesis.pdf.

Burgess, Jean. 2010. "Remediating Vernacular Creativity: Photography and Cultural Citizenship in the Flickr Photo-Sharing Network." In *Spaces of Vernacular Creativity: Rethinking the Cultural Economy*, edited by Tim Edensor, Deborah Leslie, Steve Millington, and Norma M. Rantisi. Routledge Studies in Human Geography 30. Routledge.

Edensor, Tim, and Steve Millington. 2019. "Spaces of Vernacular Creativity Reconsidered." In *Creative Placemaking: Research, Theory and Practice*, 1st ed., edited by Cara Courage and Anita McKeown. Routledge Studies in Human Geography. Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315104607>.

Edensor, Tim, Deborah Leslie, Steve Millington, and Norma M. Rantisi. 2010. "Introduction: Rethinking Creativity: Critiquing the Creative Class Thesis." In *Spaces of Vernacular Creativity: Rethinking the Cultural Economy*, edited by Tim Edensor, Deborah Leslie, Steve Millington, and Norma M. Rantisi. Routledge Studies in Human Geography 30. Routledge.

Graeber, David. 2008. "On Cosmpolitanism and (Vernacular) Democratic Creativity: Or, There Never Was a West." In *Anthropology and the New Cosmopolitanism: Rooted, Feminist and Vernacular Perspectives*, edited by Pnina Werbner. ASA Monographs 45. Berg.

Literat, Ioana. 2017. "Contemporary Creativity Online: An Examination of the Interplay between Art and Vernacular Creativity on the Internet." *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research* 18.
<https://spir.aoir.org/ojs/index.php/spir/article/view/10077>.

Milner, Ryan M. 2013. "Media Lingua Franca: Fixity, Novelty, and Vernacular Creativity in Internet Memes." *AoIR Selected Papers of Internet Research* 14 (October): 1–5.

Werbner, Pnina. 2008. "Introduction: Towards a New Cosmopolitan Anthropology." In *Anthropology and the New Cosmopolitanism: Rooted, Feminist and Vernacular Perspectives*, edited by Pnina Werbner. ASA Monographs 45. Berg.

